

A MEDITATION ROLE OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP IN BRINGING SOCIO-POLITICAL STABILITY IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact that transformational leadership has on the work outcomes of workers, such as their work performances and feelings of burnout on the job, as well as their working behaviors at the workplace, such as social loafing. In addition to this, it investigates the role that intrinsic motivation plays as a mediator between transformational leadership and the other characteristics that were indicated. In order to obtain data from the 308 workers now working in the telecommunications industry, a cross-sectional survey was carried out. In order to evaluate the hypotheses, the Model 4 of Process Hayes was used. This model was used to assess both the direct and indirect impacts that transformational leadership has on workers' work results and their working behavior. According to the findings, transformational leadership has a significantly favorable link with mediator intrinsic motivation. This was shown to be the case. The findings also led researchers to the conclusion that transformative leadership has a favorable and substantial association with workplace performance. On the other hand, there is a connection, although a tangential and small one, between transformative leadership and workplace burnout as well as social loafing. Therefore, it is possible to state that organizational leaders need to have transformational attributes, and one way to develop these attributes is by getting to know their employees well. A transformational leader is able to inspire their employees to achieve the outcomes that have been anticipated or that are significant. Once they have been properly taught, workers are then given the authority to make choices on certain duties, which boosts their sense of self-confidence.

Introduction

Leadership is very necessary in the field of education since incremental changes need to be implemented at extremely frequent intervals. Students are the product of educational institutions, and educational institutions have a responsibility to impart to students the necessary aspects of leadership training (Tahseen, 2019). The teaching staff has to have the capacity to lead in addition to having knowledge and a firm grasp on the subject matter. This is because the teacher needs to have the ability to tolerate, as well as the ability to compromise and work with others. The educational system in Punjab is in desperate need of adopting the transformational leadership model since it is the most effective type of administration currently available (Danish, 2019).

The transformative leader serves as a teacher and guide for the people who follow them. A transformational leader places an emphasis, in addition to the importance of collaboration, on the capabilities and talents of every individual in the business. This is due to the fact that individual capability is essential to the success of the organization. Second, it is essential to have inspiring motivation in order to get an amazing result from the workers. This is due to the fact that the followers will put forth their best efforts if the leader communicates something to the employees that is both inspirational and motivating. In addition, a transformational leader is one who adheres to the belief that a positive attitude should be maintained even in the face of the gravest of challenges. This is due to the fact that a positive attitude encourages employees to put forth their best efforts in order to meet the objectives of the organization. (Tahseen, 2015).

It is the process by which a leader motivates the members of the group to modify their expectations, attitudes, and motives with regard to the goals of the organization. The followers are changed by the transformational leader into caring for each other and working for the welfare of the group. (Morgan, 2012).

Literature Review:

In the following study of the relevant literature, we are going to explore the transformative leadership and influential aspects of inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration. It is vital to take a quick glance at the evolution of leadership theory in order to comprehend transformational leadership. Transformational leadership adds a new facet to the leadership toolkit that has been developed over the years. The transformational leader is the one who influences his followers to compromise on their self-interest for the sake of the organization while simultaneously elevating "the followers' level of need on Maslow's (1954) hierarchy from lower-level concerns for safety and security to higher-level needs for achievement and self-actualization." [Citation needed] In order to bring about beneficial changes in the educational system of Pakistan, and more especially in the province of Punjab, transformational leadership plays an essential role. The group of instructors must have varying levels of knowledge, abilities, and ability since they come from a variety of various backgrounds, and the difference between professionals brings about unfavorable changes in a certain subject. When it comes to the education of faculty members, the importance of transformational leadership and transformational instruction cannot be overstated. The success or failure of the pupils serves as the only criterion for determining the efficiency of the teaching personnel. The highly gifted and competent pupils are a reflection of the efficiency of the teaching team (Aga, 2016). The transformational leader affects change in the educational system by establishing a mission that seeks to improve the student's capacity for learning and by ensuring that the institution's classrooms and overall atmosphere are conducive to teaching and learning. To establish the work ethics in the educational sector, however, strong leadership is absolutely necessary. In addition, the education system in the province of Punjab is confronted with three significant problems that need to be handled. To begin, one of the most significant problems is the dearth of good educational opportunities. This specific problem cannot be handled without the appropriate direction and leadership from those in authority positions further above. Training that improves both the teaching staff's practical abilities and their capacity for intellectual thought is required for the teaching staff. Because the educator has to have the capacity to teach and control over the atmosphere of the classroom, individual attention is of the utmost importance in the field of

education. Second, there is a significant problem in the educational department caused by disagreements in viewpoints held by members of the staff. In order to solve this specific problem, an appropriate strategy for managing disagreements needs to be put into place. In conclusion, the gender gap is the most significant obstacle to overcome when it comes to the effectiveness of the teaching personnel in Punjab. In order to significantly advance the state of education in Pakistan, gender parity is an absolutely necessary component. The condition of gender disparity can be improved significantly with the help of transformational leadership's potential contribution.

To successfully manage the dispute in the education sector, transformational leadership is absolutely necessary. The disagreement might be attributed to either the educational policies or the employee training programs. The policies are notable for a handful of important aspects. To begin, the teaching staff has to be provided with all they need in order to provide useful content for the pupils. Second, the employees have received the appropriate training to ensure the cleanliness of the classroom as well as the rest of the building. Consider, for example, the effective use of the classroom's guidelines. The transformational leader influences change inside the company through making improvements to the organization's general structure. In addition, avoiding disagreement and searching for the optimal answer are two of the most important responsibilities that a leader must do. In addition, the only way to successfully settle the disagreement is to make accommodations for gender-based difficulties, which is an essential component of transformational leadership strategies. In addition to this, the instructor serves as an example for the pupils, and a healthy connection between instructor and pupil can only be achieved by maintaining a favorable atmosphere (Ghasabeh, 2015). To successfully navigate the difficult circumstances, transformational leadership and conflict resolution solutions are very necessary. The researchers, on the other hand, believe that leadership qualities can be honed and improved inside an organization. Tolerance is the most important leadership characteristic in educational institutions since it reflects the conduct of workers in a company; thus, tolerance is one of the most important leadership qualities in organizations (Zhang, 2015). There is a need for education, direction, and leadership in order to resolve the conflicts within the system. This is due to the fact that the result of the system may be improved via the management of conflicts and the implementation of positive changes within the system. The faculty and staff in higher education have little understanding of the creative process. In addition, those who work in higher education need to be creative and have the capacity to communicate knowledge effectively as a fundamental prerequisite. The positive shifts brought about by adopting a transformational leadership style, together with the adjustments made to the policies and plans, were very important in the process of creating an education system of a high standard (Banks, 2016). According to the findings of the experts, it is impossible for any part of the nation to be successful without an effective leadership plan (Ghasabeh, 2015). In addition, a competent leader has a number of other skills. To begin, the leader needs to be a member of the team in order to participate in a concerted effort to accomplish the goals. Second, the person in charge has to exhibit an attitude that inspires others to work hard. Incentives, both financial and non-financial, are contributing to the advantages (Tahseen, 2019). The maximum of the country's income cycle is where the financial benefits lie, since this is where the most money can be made. In addition, an increase in the revenue stream is only possible if the organization is prepared to provide a service of a sufficient standard. The sole product of the education system in the nation is its student body. Students are required to possess attributes of leadership since such abilities are

essential for successfully navigating the difficult circumstances facing the nation (Zhang, 2015). Because the education sector of the country is the driver of the whole society, and because a lack in the educational sector can be a disastrous element for society, the non-financial benefits are essential for the institution. The non-financial component relates to the level of productivity achieved by the organization, and includes factors such as a favorable working environment that is in line with the established cultural norms and values. It is essential, in order to preserve a wholesome working environment, for organizations to have both norms and values. In addition, a healthy working environment can be created by having excellent leadership qualities and having a working environment that encourages collaboration. In the field of education that the country is responsible for, having staff members who are willing to work together and cooperate can be an invaluable asset. Respect for one another among the workers is necessary for the maintenance of a healthy relationship. Respecting one another's ideals and principles is an essential component, which is even more important. The teaching staff comes from a variety of cultural and ethnic backgrounds, each of which is represented here. In spite of this, the fact that people from a variety of different backgrounds are able to share their unique perspectives is a sign that the institutional perspective is improving. The diversity of opinions is to the advantage of both the established systems and the overall society.

Hypothesis:

H1: The transformational style of leadership has a favorable and substantial influence on the link between conflict management and the performance of the faculty.

Sample and Data Collecting:

The information was gathered from individuals working in the telecommunications industry through the use of a survey that was conducted via emails, online surveys, and printed questionnaires. The sampling method was convenience sampling. The purpose of the study, as well as the participants' assurances of privacy and secrecy about their replies, were communicated to the people who took part in the research. The respondents were given the assurance that their information would not be evaluated by any other persons outside those who were authorized to do so. Following the elimination of the responses that contained duplicates, outliers, and gaps in data, we were left with 308 valid responses for the subsequent analysis. The demographic information pertaining to the respondents is shown in Table 1.

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	269	87.3
Female	39	12.7
Age		
20–25	2	0.6
26–30	77	25
31–35	81	26.3
36–40	95	30.8

Above 40	53	17.2
Qualification		
Diploma	2	0.6
Intermediate	17	5.5
Bachelors	135	43.8
Masters	153	49.7
Ph.D.	10	5

Data Analysis

After the data collection was complete, the reliability and correlation were determined with the help of the SPSS software. Hayes Process Model 4 was used to conduct the research model's validation.

Finding & Discussion:

According to the findings of this research study, transformational leadership has a strong and beneficial association with the intrinsic motivation of workers. The idea that transformational leadership boosts employee motivation and develops positive psychological states such as meaningfulness of work, experienced responsibility for the outcomes, and knowledge of work results is supported by previous research. This finding suggests that transformational leadership has a positive impact on organizational performance. It indicates that transformational leadership directly exerts its influence by helping employees or followers to think more positively about themselves and their tasks, by improving the quality of their relationships, and by creating environments that are fair, respectful, and supportive. All of these factors contribute positively toward employee's self-motivation toward his or her work, which is a positive result of transformational leadership. The positive aspects of transformational leadership are responsible for bringing about positive psychological states in employees by increasing their levels of intrinsic motivation. When it comes to their job performances, employees who have higher levels of intrinsic motivation are more productive and efficient than their peers. It is expected of them that they will become responsive, and that they will carry out their duties effectively. The findings of this study revealed a significant and favorable relationship between transformational leadership and the avoidance of occupational burnout via intrinsic motivation. The employee experiences less exhaustion and more motivation as a result of a transformational leader's indication of support for honest and fair matters associated with employees. Employees who are driven by the enjoyment and interest that they get from their work are said to be intrinsically motivated. Employees who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to put in long hours at work, report feeling less fatigue and emotional exhaustion, and have a greater desire to participate in the organization. In the end, an investigation into the ways in which transformational leadership might influence social loafing was conducted via the lens of intrinsic drive. The findings suggest that despite the fact that social loafing has a significant and unfavorable relationship with transformational leaders, the indirect relationship between the two through intrinsic motivation

does not hold any significant weight. The reason for this could be due to the direct and strong association between transformational leaders and social loafing. According to the article, "Transformational Leaders Effectively Inspire Followers to Identify with a Mission While Rallying Them to Work Together to Achieve Organizational Objectives," transformational leaders effectively inspire followers to identify with a mission while rallying them to In addition, other factors, such as workload, organizational culture, length of employment, and so on, can have a significant impact on the extent to which employees engage in social loafing.

The results of our research also have a number of consequences that are applicable to businesses. When transformational leaders recognize the significance of intrinsic motivation for workers, they will adopt behaviors that are conducive to the growth of employees' intrinsic motivation in the workplace. These behaviors include providing opportunities for employees to take ownership of their work and being recognized for their contributions. The findings of this research indicated that transformational leadership, which involves promoting intrinsic motivation in employees, is responsible for creating an atmosphere that is free of stress and conducive to good employee performance. One approach that managers can take to demonstrate these behaviors is to work toward the goal of motivating employees based on the inherent joy and satisfaction that they experience in their work. One more way to boost the intrinsic motivation of workers and increase their involvement in the success of an organization is to value the contributions of workers and communicate the organization's goals and objectives to those workers. In addition, it is very important for the leaders of an organization to be transformed by becoming well informed of their employees. This is because a transformational leader can inspire their followers to accomplish results that are either unexpected or remarkable. After receiving proper instruction, it vested the workers with the authority to make their own choices and grants them autonomy over the tasks they were assigned to perform. Because transformational leaders are able to improve a group's well-being and motivation level through excellent connection, they can inspire workers to find better ways of achieving a goal; leadership can mobilize people into groups that can get work done; and morale, because transformational leaders can inspire workers to find better ways of achieving a goal. The findings of this study emphasized the importance of designing leadership coaching and training program in order to develop transformational leadership. These program may include "programs for communication, motivation, and brainstorming, to train employees with the necessary resources to be more articulate and inspirational as well as to think out of the box," according to one of the findings of the study.

Conclusion:

This research makes a contribution to the field of organizational behavior by enhancing our knowledge of how a transformational leader can improve employees' positive work outcomes by improving their intrinsic motivation. This contributes to our understanding of how a transformational leader can improve organizational performance. In addition to this, an increase in employees' intrinsic motivation will develop their positive work outcomes by simultaneously reducing employee burnout and work stress while simultaneously leading to an increase in employees' work performance. We have high hopes that our research will inspire further research and efforts to deepen our understanding of this subject area.

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